

MORE ABOUT $L(\delta^*$ -OPEN, OPEN) MAPPINGS

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Abstract: In this paper, we further study some properties of $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) mapping, using, δ^* -convergence of nets and filters in a space. We study δ^* -quotient topology, δ^* -quotient space with some separation and covering axioms in connection to these mappings.

Key words: δ -open, δ^* -open sets; $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) mappings and δ^* -ultra normal, δ^* -ultra normal spaces

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1. Introduction

In 1963, Levine [1] introduced the notion of semi-open sets as a generalization of open sets and using semi-open sets, semi-continuous functions are introduced. In 1966, Velicko [7] introduced the concepts of θ -open and δ -open sets and obtained their properties. In 1982, Munshi and Bassan [3] introduced the notion of super continuous mappings. In 1987, Singal and Yadav [5] introduced a weak form of δ -open sets, called δ^* -open sets. In 1990, Sundar Lal [6] introduced the notion of ultra-normal spaces as a generalization of normal spaces in topological spaces and shown that ultra-normality is preserved under continuous and clopen maps. Recently, Bhopal Singh Sharma and Hamant Kumar [4] studied the concept of $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) mappings and various characterizations along with some preservation properties of the new mappings.

2. Preliminaries

A mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **$L(\delta^*$ -open, open)** mapping [1] if at each $x \in X$ and to every open set M containing $f(x)$, there exists a δ^* -open set N containing x such that $f(N) \subset M$. Singal and Yadav [5] (resp. Velicko [7]) defined $H \subset X$ to be **δ^* -open** (resp. **δ -open**) if for each $x \in H$, there exists a clopen (resp. regular open) set G such that $x \in G \subset H$. A set A is **δ^* -closed** (resp. **δ -closed**) if $X - A$ is δ^* -open (resp. δ -open) and **δ^* -clopen** (resp. **δ -clopen**) if it is both δ^* -open (resp. δ -open) and δ^* -closed (resp. δ -closed). The authors [5] showed that the collection of all δ^* -open sets in a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , denoted by δ^* - $O(X, \mathfrak{T})$ is a topology \mathfrak{T}^* on X , called **O-dimensionalization** of \mathfrak{T} . They further showed $T = T^*$ iff the space (X, T) is O-dimensional space. $A \subset X$ is said to be **semi-open** [1] (resp. **feebly open** [2]) if $G \subset A \subset \text{cl}(G)$ (resp. $G \subset A \subset \text{s-cl}(G)$, where s-cl denotes semi closure) for some open set G . A is **θ -open** [7] if for each $x \in A$, there exists an open set G such that $x \in G \subset \text{cl}(G) \subset A$. The smallest δ^* -closed set containing A is called **δ^* -closure** of A , denoted by δ^* - $\text{cl}(A)$ and the largest δ^* -open set in A is called **δ^* -interior** of A , denoted by δ^* - $\text{int}(A)$.

3. δ^* -convergence of nets and filters

3.1 Definition. A point $x \in X$ is said to be δ^* -adherent point of $A \subset X$ iff every δ^* -open set containing x , contains a point of A , and a net $\{x_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in D}$, where (D, \geq) is a directed set, in a space (X, T) is said to be δ^* -convergent at $x \in X$ iff the net is eventually in each δ^* -open set containing x .

If $A \subset X$ and $x \in X$, then $x \in \text{cl}(A)$ iff there exists a net in A converging to x . Now we generalize this concept for δ^* -convergence.

3.2 Theorem. If $A \subset X$ and $x \in X$ then $x \in \delta^*\text{-cl}(A)$ iff there exists a net in A , δ^* -converging to x .

Proof. If $\{x_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in D}$ is a net in A , δ^* -converging to x , then the net is eventually in every δ^* -open set V containing x , or there exists a $\lambda_0 \in D$: $\lambda \geq \lambda_0$ implies $x_\lambda \in V$, particularly, $x_{\lambda_0} \in V \cap A$. Thus every δ^* -open set V containing x , contains a point of A , so, x is a δ^* -adherent point of A and consequently $x \in \delta^*\text{-cl}(A)$.

Conversely, if $x \in \delta^*\text{-cl}(A)$, then every δ^* -open set containing x must intersect A . Let δ^*_x be the collection of all δ^* -open sets containing x . Then, δ^*_x is directed by the inclusion relation. Since $V \cap A \neq \emptyset$ for every V in δ^*_x by the axiom of choice for each V in δ^*_x , we may choose a point $x_0(V)$ in $V \cap A$. Now the mapping $f : \delta^*_x \rightarrow A$ defined by $f(V) = x_0(V)$ for each V in δ^*_x is a net in A δ^* -converging to x . To see the δ^* -convergence, if V is any δ^* -open set containing x , then for each W in δ^*_x such that $W \subset V$, we have, $f(W) = x_0(W) \in W \cap A \subset V$.

3.3 Definition. A filter \mathfrak{F} on X is said to be δ^* -convergent at $x \in X$ if every δ^* -open neighbourhood of x is a member of \mathfrak{F} , and we say that x is δ^* -limit point of \mathfrak{F} , written as $\mathfrak{F} \xrightarrow{\delta^*} x$. The set of all δ^* -limit points of filter \mathfrak{F} , is denoted by $\delta^*\text{-lim}(\mathfrak{F})$. The collection of all δ^* -neighbourhoods of x is a filter on x , called δ^* -neighbourhood filter of x denoted by $\delta^*_x\text{-nhd filter}$. Obviously, $\delta^*_x\text{-nhd filter} \xrightarrow{\delta^*} x$.

A filter base $\beta = \{B_\lambda\}$ on X is said to be δ^* -convergent at $x \in X$ iff the filter generated by the base, δ^* -converges to x . Equivalently, filter base $\beta = \{B_\lambda\}$ on a space X , δ^* -converges to $x \in X$ iff for each δ^* -open set V containing x , there is B_λ in β such that $B_\lambda \subset V$.

3.4 Theorem. For a filter \mathfrak{F} on X , the following are equivalent.

- \mathfrak{F} , δ^* -converges to x in X .
- Each δ^* -neighbourhood of x is in \mathfrak{F} .
- \mathfrak{F} is finer than $\delta^*_x\text{-nhd filter}$ on X for each x in X .
- For every δ^* -neighbourhood N of x , there is $F \in \mathfrak{F}$ such that $F \subset N$.

3.5 Theorem. Every filter \mathfrak{F} on an indiscrete space X , δ^* -converges to every point of X .

Proof. Since the $\delta^*_x\text{-nhd filter} = \{X\}$ and $X \in \mathfrak{F}$, it follows that \mathfrak{F} , δ^* -converges to x for all x in X .

3.6 Corollary. The δ^* -convergent filters on a discrete space are the δ^* -neighbourhood filters only.

3.7 Corollary. Let \mathfrak{F} be a filter on X , δ^* -converging to x in X , then every filter \mathfrak{F}^1 finer than \mathfrak{F} also δ^* -converges to x .

3.8 Theorem. If $A \subset X$ and $x \in X$, then $x \in \delta^*\text{-cl}(A)$ iff there exists a filter base on A , δ^* -converging to x .

Proof. Let $\beta = \{B_\lambda\}$ be a filter base on A , which δ^* -converges to x , so, for each δ^* -open set V containing x , there exists B_λ in β such that $B_\lambda \subset V$. Since B_λ is nonempty subset of A , it follows that V contains a point of A . Hence x is a δ^* -adherent point of A and so, $x \in \delta^*\text{-cl}(A)$.

Conversely, let $x \in \delta^*\text{-cl}(A)$ implies every δ^* -open set containing x must intersect A . Now consider the collection $\beta = \{A \cap V : V \text{ is } \delta^*\text{-open set containing } x\}$. Obviously β is a filter base on A , δ^* -converging to x .

3.9 Theorem. Let T and T° be two topologies on X . T is finer than T° iff a filter \mathfrak{F} , δ^* -converging to x in T implies the same in T° and hence $T = T^\circ$ iff both topologies have the same, δ^* -convergent filters and the corresponding limits.

Proof. If T is finer than T° and \mathfrak{F} , δ^* -converges to x in T . Then δ^*_x -nhd filter in T° is a subset of δ^*_x -nhd filter in T and hence is in \mathfrak{F} .

Conversely let filter \mathfrak{F} , δ^* -converges to x in T , this implies \mathfrak{F} , δ^* -converges to x in T° . Let $S \subset X$. If $x \in \delta^*\text{-cl}(S)$, then there exists a filter base $\beta = \{B_\lambda\}$ on S , δ^* -converging to x in T and hence in T° and so, $x \in \delta^*_{T^\circ}\text{-cl}(S)$. Thus T is finer than T° , rest part is obvious.

3.10 Theorem. For a mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$, the following are equivalent:

- f is $L(\delta^*\text{-open, open})$
- For each $x \in X$ and each net $\{x_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in D}$ δ^* -converging to x , the net $\{f(x_\lambda)\}_{\lambda \in D}$ converges to $f(x)$.
- For each $x \in X$ and each net $\{x_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in D}$ converging to x in X^* , the O -dimensionalization of X , $\{f(x_\lambda)\}$ converges to $f(x)$.
- For each $x \in X$, and each filter base β , δ^* -converging to x , $f(\beta)$ converges to $f(x)$.
- For each $x \in X$ and each filter base β , converging to x in X^* , $f(\beta)$ converges to $f(x)$.

Proof. (a) \Leftrightarrow (b) Let $x \in X$ and $\{x_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in D}$ δ^* -converging to x . If V is any open set containing $f(x)$, then $x \in f^{-1}(V)$, a δ^* -open set. Since the net δ^* -converges to x , so, there exists $\lambda_0 : \lambda \geq \lambda_0 \Rightarrow x_\lambda \in f^{-1}(V)$ or $f(x_\lambda) \in V$ for all $\lambda \geq \lambda_0$. Thus the net $\{f(x_\lambda)\}_{\lambda \in D}$ converges to $f(x)$. Conversely, if $x \in \delta^*\text{-cl}(A)$, then there exists a net $\{x_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in D}$ in A δ^* -converging to x (**3.2 Theorem**). By hypothesis, net $\{f(x_\lambda)\}_{\lambda \in D}$ converges to $f(x)$, so $f(x) \in \text{cl}(f(A))$. Thus $f(\delta^*\text{-cl}(A)) \subset \text{cl}(f(A))$ for each $A \subset X$.

(a) \Leftrightarrow (d) Let V be open set containing $f(x)$, then x is in δ^* -open set $f^{-1}(V)$. So, there exists $B_\lambda \in \beta$, such that $B_\lambda \subset f^{-1}(V) \Rightarrow f(B_\lambda) \subset V$. Conversely, let $x \in \delta^*\text{-cl}(A)$, then there exists a filter base $\beta = \{B_\lambda\}$ on A δ^* -converging to x , (**Theorem 3.8**). Hence the filter base $f(\beta)$ on $f(A)$ converges to $f(x)$, so $f(x) \in \text{cl}(f(A))$. Thus $f(\delta^*\text{-cl}(A)) \subset \text{cl}(f(A))$ for each $A \subset X$. So, f is $L(\delta^*\text{-open, open})$. The rest is obvious.

4. δ^* -quotient topology and δ^* -quotient space

In view of the concept of δ -quotient topology [3], we may generalize this to δ^* -quotient topology.

4.1 Definitin. Let f be a mapping from a topological space X on to a set Y . Then the collection \mathcal{U} of subsets A of Y , for which, A is in \mathcal{U} iff $f^{-1}(A)$ is δ^* -open in X , is a topology on Y , called the **δ^* -quotient topology** on Y and (Y, \mathcal{U}) is called the **δ^* -quotient space**. Obviously, the δ^* -quotient topology is dependent on the map $f : X \rightarrow Y$. Also, F is closed in (Y, \mathcal{U}) , the δ^* -quotient space iff $f^{-1}(F)$ is δ^* -closed in X .

4.2 Definition. A map is called **D (δ^* -open, open)** (resp. **D (open, δ^* -open)**), **D (δ^* -closed, closed)**, **D (closed, δ^* -closed)**) if it maps δ^* -open (resp. open, δ^* -closed, closed) set onto open (resp. δ^* -open, closed, δ^* -closed) set respectively. Moreover, a bijection is called **δ^* -homeomorphism** if f and f^{-1} are L (δ^* -open, open).

4.3 Theorem. For a bijection $f : X \rightarrow Y$, the following are equivalent.

- f is δ^* -homeomorphism.
- f is L (δ^* -open, open) and D (open, δ^* -open).
- f is L (δ^* -open, open) and D (closed, δ^* -closed).
- f is L (δ^* -open, open) and D (clopen, δ^* -clopen).

4.4 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{V})$ be a surjection, where \mathcal{V} is the δ^* -quotient topology on Y . Then f is L (δ^* -open, open) and D (δ^* -open, open). Moreover \mathcal{V} is the largest topology on Y , which makes f , L (δ^* -open, open).

Proof. By definition, f is L (δ^* -open, open). Let G be δ^* -open in X , Then $G = f^{-1}(H)$, for some H open in Y and $f(G) = H$. Thus f is D (δ^* -open, open). If \mathcal{W} is any topology on Y such that $f : X \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{W})$ is L (δ^* -open, open). Let G be \mathcal{W} -open set in Y , then $f^{-1}(G)$ is δ^* -open in X , hence G is \mathcal{V} -open. So $\mathcal{W} \subset \mathcal{V}$.

4.5 Corollary. If $f : X \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{V})$ is L (δ^* -open, open), D (δ^* -open, open) surjection, then the topology \mathcal{V} on Y is the δ^* -quotient topology.

4.6 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow (Y, \mathcal{V})$ is a map, \mathcal{V} is δ^* -quotient topology then $g : (Y, \mathcal{V}) \rightarrow (Z, \mathcal{W})$ is continuous iff the composition map $g \circ f$ is L (δ^* -open, open).

Proof. Let G be open in (Z, \mathcal{W}) , then $(g \circ f)^{-1}(G) = f^{-1}(g^{-1}(G))$ is δ^* -open in X . So $g^{-1}(G)$ is open in (Y, \mathcal{V}) . Thus g is continuous and the converse is obvious.

5. L (δ^* -open, open) maps with separation and covering axioms

5.1 Theorem. If f and g are L (δ^* -open, open) maps from a space X into a T_2 -space Y , then the set $A = \{x : f(x) = g(x)\}$ is δ^* -closed in X .

Proof. If $y \in X - A$, then $f(y) \neq g(y)$, and hence, there exist disjoint open sets P and Q in Y , such that $g(y) \in P$ and $f(y) \in Q$. Since f and g are $L(\delta^*$ -open, open), so $E = f^{-1}(Q) \cap g^{-1}(P)$ is δ^* -open and $E \subset X - A$. Thus A is δ^* -closed.

5.2 Corollary. If f and g agree on a set G such that δ^* -cl(G) = X in **Therom5.1**, then $f = g$.

If open sets are replaced by δ^* -open sets in the definitions of T_0, T_1 , and T_2 spaces, then we have δ^* - T_0, δ^* - T_1 and δ^* - T_2 spaces respectively.

5.3 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) injection into a T_2 -space then every pair of distinct points of X is separated by means of disjoint δ^* -open sets i.e. X is δ^* - T_2 .

Proof. If $x \neq y$, in X , then there exists disjoint open sets G and H in Y such that $f(x) \in G$ and $f(y) \in H$. Since, f is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open), so, $f^{-1}(G)$ and $f^{-1}(H)$ are the required sets.

5.4 Corollary. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) injection into a T_0 (or T_1) space, then X is δ^* - T_0 (or δ^* - T_1) space.

5.5 Definition. $A \subset X$ is said to be δ^* -compact if every δ^* -open cover of A has a finite sub cover. A space is δ^* -compact if it is δ^* -compact as a subset of itself. Obviously, every δ^* -closed subset of a δ^* -compact space is δ^* -compact.

5.6 Theorem. The $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) image of a δ^* -compact space is compact.

Proof. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) surjection and X a δ^* -compact space. If $C_1 = \{G_\lambda : \lambda \in \Lambda\}$ is an open cover of Y , then $C_2 = \{f^{-1}(G_\lambda) : \lambda \in \Lambda\}$ is a δ^* -open cover of X . Since, X is δ^* -compact, C_2 must have a finite subcover in other words C_1 has a finite subcover. So, Y is compact.

5.7 Corollary. Every $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) map from a δ^* -compact space X onto a T_2 -space is $D(\delta^*$ -closed, closed).

5.8 Definition. A map is called **I (δ^* -compact, compact)** if inverse image of a compact set is δ^* -compact set.

5.9 Theorem. Every $L(\delta^*$ -open, open) map from a δ^* -compact space into a T_2 space is **I (δ^* -compact, compact)**.

A space is defined [6] to be **ultra normal** if any two disjoint closed sets are contained in disjoint clopen sets.

5.10 Theorem. A space X is ultra normal iff for any closed set F and an open set G containing F , there exists a clopen set V such that $F \subset V \subset G$.

Proof. Since G is open, so, $X - G$ is closed such that $F \cap (X - G) = \emptyset$, by ultra normality of X , there exist disjoint clopen sets U and V , such that $X - G \subset U$ and $F \subset V$. or $F \subset V \subset G$.

Conversely, let A and B be disjoint closed sets, this implies $A \subset X - B$, by hypothesis, there exists a clopen set V , such that $A \subset V \subset X - B$. Thus V and $X - V$ are the required disjoint clopen sets.

5.11 Corollary. A space is ultra-normal iff each open neighbourhood G of a closed set F , contains a clopen neighbourhood V of F .

5.12 Definition. A space is said to be δ^* -normal (resp. δ^* -normal) if any pair of disjoint δ^* -closed (resp. closed) sets are contained in disjoint open (resp. δ^* -open) sets respectively.

5.13 Definition. A space is said to be δ^* -ultra normal (resp. δ^* -ultra normal) if any pair of disjoint δ^* -closed (resp. closed) sets are contained in disjoint clopen (resp. δ^* -clopen) sets.

The author [5] has shown that ultra normality is preserved under continuous and clopen maps. Here, we have,

5.14 Theorem. Let X be δ^* -normal (or normal) and $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be δ^* -homeomorphism, then Y is δ^* -normal.

Proof. If A and B are disjoint closed sets in Y then $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are δ^* -closed sets in X , a δ^* -normal space, so there exist disjoint open sets P and Q such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset P$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset Q$ or $A \subset f(P)$ and $B \subset f(Q)$. So $f(P)$ and $f(Q)$ are the required δ^* -open sets.

5.15 Theorem. Let X be δ^* -ultra normal (or ultra normal) and $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be δ^* -homeomorphism then Y is δ^* -ultra normal.

5.16 Theorem. A space X is δ^* -ultra normal iff for each pair A, B of disjoint closed subsets of X , there exists an I (δ^* -clopen, open) map $f : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that $f(A) = 0$ and $f(B) = 1$.

Proof. Parallel to Urysohn's lemma and **Theorem 6** [6].

5.17 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is L (δ^* -open, open) and $A \subset X$ is δ^* -compact. Then $f(A)$ is compact.

Proof. Let \mathfrak{V} be any open cover of $f(A)$, then to each $a \in A$, there exists an open set $V_a \in \mathfrak{V}$ such that $f(a) \in V_a$. Since f is L (δ^* -open, open) so, there exist a δ^* -open set U_a containing a such that $f(U_a) \subset V_a$. Now the collection $\{U_a : a \in A\}$ is δ^* -open cover of δ^* -compact set A so, $A \subset \cup_{i=1}^n U_{a_i}$ for finitely many a_i 's. Hence $f(A) \subset \cup_{i=1}^n f(U_i) \subset \cup_{i=1}^n V_{a_i}$. Hence $f(A)$ is compact.

5.18 Definition. A space X is called **ultra- T_1** if distinct points x, y in X , have clopen neighbourhoods G and H of x and y respectively such that $y \notin G$ and $x \notin H$.

5.19 Theorem. Every L (δ^* -open, open) map carries a δ^* -compact set A on to a δ^* -closed set in an ultra- T_1 spaces.

Proof. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be the L (δ^* -open, open) map and A be δ^* -compact in X . Let $y \notin f(A)$. Since, Y is ultra- T_1 , each $f(x) \in f(A)$ has a clopen neighbourhood $V_{f(x)}$ such that $y \notin V_{f(x)}$. Since f is L (δ^* -open, open),

there exists a δ^* -open neighbourhood U_x of x such that $f(U_x) \subset V_{f(x)}$. Now $\{U_x : x \in A\}$ is δ^* -open cover of δ^* -compact set A , so $A \subset \cup_{i=1}^n U_{x_i}$ for some finite x_i 's. Hence $f(A) \subset \cup_{i=1}^n f(U_{x_i}) \subset \cup_{i=1}^n V_{f(x_i)}$. $Z = Y - \cup_{i=1}^n V_{f(x_i)}$ is clopen set containing y such that $y \in Z \subset Y - f(A)$. Thus $f(A)$ is δ^* -closed.

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